

Erasmus+ Programme

Key Action 2 - Cooperation Partnerships in School Education

REPORT

R3.3.6

Co- Creation Workshops

Co-funded by
the European Union

A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education

Grant Agreement No. 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000090043

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Short Description	This document reports on the process, activities, and outcomes of the ASAP Co-Creation Workshops carried out within the Erasmus+ ASAP project. It describes five transnational workshops implemented between March 2023 and February 2025 and their role in the co-design, testing and consolidation of the ASAP Educational Model and Programme. The report outlines the methodological approach adopted and highlights how research evidence, educational practice and piloting activities were progressively integrated through participatory and practice-oriented co-creation processes.

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1. Introduction

This report presents the process, activities and outcomes of the ASAP Co-Creation Workshops (CCWs), implemented within Work Package 3 of the ASAP project as a core methodological and operational component supporting the development of the ASAP Educational Model and Programme.

Conceived as iterative, transnational, and transdisciplinary learning spaces, the CCWs were designed to foster structured dialogue and collaboration among project partners, educators, experts, school communities and, in selected phases, pre-adolescents. Across the project lifecycle, the workshops functioned as hinge points between research (WP2), educational design (WP3), piloting and evaluation (WP4), educator training (WP5), participatory pathways (WP6), and policy-oriented reflection (WP7).

Through a progressive sequence of five workshops held between 2023 and 2025 in all partner countries, the CCWs supported the co-construction, testing, refinement, and consolidation of the ASAP Educational Programme, ensuring its grounding in research evidence, educational practice, and real school contexts. This report documents the evolution of the co-creation process, highlighting the specific focus, activities, and outcomes of each workshop, and provides an integrated overview of how the CCWs contributed to shaping the project's educational, methodological, and strategic trajectory.

2. The ASAP Co-Creation Workshops

2.1. Overview of the Co-Creation Workshop

The ASAP Co-Creation Workshops represent a core methodological component of the project and a key driver of integration across Work Packages. Rather than isolated events, the CCWs were conceived as a progressive process, in which each workshop built on previous findings, discussions and outputs, while preparing the ground for subsequent phases.

Methodologically, the CCWs combined transdisciplinary dialogue, participatory design, reflective practice, and hands-on experimentation. Each workshop integrated multiple formats—such as Transdisciplinary Labs, expert inputs, facilitated group work, testing sessions and collective evaluation moments—designed to support both conceptual reflection and concrete educational development. At the same time, the CCWs functioned as structured spaces of listening, mutual learning and exchange with local target groups (teachers, school leaders, students and families), as well as with invited experts, ensuring that educational design remained closely connected to real school contexts, professional experiences and emerging needs.

In total, five Co-Creation Workshops were implemented over the project duration: the 1st CCW in Maribor (Slovenia), the 2nd CCW in Porto (Portugal), the 3rd CCW in České Budějovice (Czechia), the 4th CCW in Zagreb (Croatia) and the 5th CCW in Milan (Italy).

Across these five workshops, the focus gradually evolved from conceptual exploration and needs analysis to the co-design and testing of learning activities, and finally to consolidation, impact assessment, educator training, and policy-oriented reflection. This iterative approach allowed the ASAP Educational Programme to be progressively refined, validated and aligned with research evidence, educators' needs, and institutional contexts, while reinforcing shared pedagogical principles such as dialogue, experience-based learning, critical thinking, and mediation.

Together, the CCWs provided a structured space for aligning educational design, implementation, and evaluation, while also strengthening collaboration among partners and supporting the sustainability and transferability of project results beyond the project duration.

2.2. 1st ASAP Co-Creation Workshop (Maribor, Slovenia)

The first ASAP Co-Creation Workshop (CCW) was held in Maribor, Slovenia, from 13 to 15 March 2023, and hosted by DOBA Business School. It represented the initial implementation of the ASAP co-creation methodology and played a key role in establishing a shared conceptual, methodological, and pedagogical framework among project partners.

Conceived as a three-day transnational and transdisciplinary learning experience, the workshop combined reflective learning, expert knowledge, and participatory co-design, and was explicitly designed to act as a hinge point between research activities (WP2), educational model and programme development (WP3) and future piloting activities (WP4).

Thematic focus and objectives

The Maribor CCW focused on the overarching topic “On the relationships between means and ends”, using media (as means themselves by definition), and digital and social media in particular, as key analytical lenses. This focus was selected as a starting point to support a critical and reflective understanding of how digital and social media function not only as neutral tools, but also as environments that actively contribute in shaping practices, identities, relationships and cognitive processes in pre-adolescents’ (and everyone’s) everyday lives.

The specific objectives of the workshop were to:

- develop a common ground and conceptual framework among partners regarding media, social media, and digital environments;
- integrate perspectives from different disciplines (education, psychology, sociology, anthropology, media studies);
- actively involve local school representatives and experts in the co-creation of project assumptions, priorities, and outputs;
- generate structured inputs for subsequent research, design, and implementation phases of the project.

Throughout the workshop, participants were encouraged to adopt a metacognitive stance, reflecting not only on *what* was discussed, but also on *how* meanings were constructed, assumptions were challenged, and knowledge was collaboratively developed.

Participants

Overall, the CCW brought together 16 project partners representatives as well as 4 Slovenian experts with expertise in digital education, media literacy, and cyberbullying prevention and 10 local school representatives, specifically teachers, which attended the third day of activities.

Both during partners only and open sessions, working groups were deliberately composed to be heterogeneous in terms of disciplinary background, professional role, country, and experience. This design choice aimed to foster cross-country comparison, mutual learning, and the emergence of transdisciplinary perspectives, while also ensuring that educational practice and school-based experiences remained central to the discussions.

CCW Activities

The workshop was structured around a sequence of Transdisciplinary Lab (T-Lab) sessions, combining expert inputs, facilitated group work, plenary discussions, and reflective wrap-up moments.

The first day was titled “Exploring media and social media” and focused on a preliminary exploration of digital/social media, framed through the lens of means and ends.

T-Lab Session 1 – “A world of media” invited participants to reflect on different forms of media and their historical evolution. Participants were divided into mixed groups, each assigned with a specific set of media (audio-visual, music-based, language-based), and asked to critically explore the relationships between means and ends associated with those media. For instance, the group working on audio-visual media was provided with a set of visual cards representing an architectural artefact, a sculpture, a fresco, a painting, scenes from black-and-white and colour films, as well as analogue and digital devices such as a photcamera, a videocamera, a digital camera and a television. Through guided group work and subsequent plenary discussion, participants analysed media shifts and transformations, questioning implicit assumptions, disciplinary perspectives and cultural narratives associated with media change. Particular attention was paid to understanding how media function not only as technical means, but also as carriers of values, practices, and social meanings.

T-Lab Session 2 – “A world of (social) media” applied the same analytical framework to specific social media platforms. In this case, participants were asked to select one social media platform (e.g. Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, TikTok, WhatsApp) and to reflect on the relationships between means and ends associated with its use. Through facilitated group work and plenary discussion, participants addressed key dimensions such as private/public, individual/collective, active/passive and physical/digital. The session explicitly encouraged participants to engage in metacognitive reflection, focusing not only on the content of the discussion but also on the reasoning processes, assumptions and perspectives adopted when analysing social media practices.

The second day, entitled “Experts talk”, deepened the analysis through expert contributions and transdisciplinary research perspectives.

During T-Lab Session 3, experts from different disciplinary backgrounds provided inputs prepared for the occasion on topics such as cognitive flexibility (A. Ocepek, DOBA), influencers and role models (I. Kanižaj, DKMK), body and self-representation (S. Digennaro, University of Cassino and Southern Lazio), the relationship between body and culture from a cognitive and anthropological perspective (M. Giordano, University of Siena), media as tools for active citizenship (A. Oliveira and T. Castro, COFAC), and the role of educators as mediators in digital and media literacy processes (L. Brzáková, ProEduca). These inputs were organised in three iterative rounds, alternated with group reflection, enabling participants to progressively integrate expert knowledge into their own conceptual understanding. Building on these discussions, participants reflected on what pre-adolescents should know about the relationships between means and ends in digital/social media contexts, and how such knowledge could be translated into educational practices.

T-Lab Session 4 focused on presenting and discussing the implications for the project of transdisciplinary research findings developed or under development by the project partners. Drawing on their respective disciplinary backgrounds and ongoing research work, partners presented key insights related, among others, to media and digital literacy, mediatisation processes, cognitive and psycho-social development of pre-adolescents, online risks and cyberbullying, as well as the role of schools, educators and families in digital education and prevention strategies. These contributions

enabled a structured discussion on the relevance of research evidence for the different project activities, fostering a collective reflection on how transdisciplinary perspectives should inform field research design, the development of the ASAP Educational Model and Programme, and future educator training activities. The research contributions discussed during this session were subsequently consolidated and further developed within the Final Desk Research Report, ensuring coherence between the CCW outcomes and the project's research framework.

The third day centred on co-creation with local school representatives and addressed the practical challenges schools face in relation to social media use and online risks among pre-adolescents.

The activities opened with a round table on “Digital education and cyberbullying prevention: existing situation, challenges, and needs in the Slovenian school context”, which brought together local experts from academia, public institutions, and civil society organisations. Contributions were provided by Maja Vičič Krabonja (Secondary School of economics and Grammar School in Maribor), Maja Vreča (ARNES), Boris Veler (Logout.org) and Benjamin Lesjak (University of Primorska, Safe.si), who offered complementary perspectives on current trends, challenges and preventive approaches related to digital education, online risks and cyberbullying in Slovenian schools. The round table helped contextualise the project themes within the national educational and institutional landscape, highlighting both existing practices and emerging needs.

Following the round table, local participants engaged in small-group discussions focused on needs analysis. School representatives shared experiences, challenges, and existing practices, while project partners facilitated the discussion to ensure alignment with project objectives.

Figure 1. Group session with teachers during the 1st ASAP Co-Creation Workshop in Maribor, Slovenia

This session generated concrete inputs concerning

- priority topics to be addressed by the ASAP project;
- knowledge and skills required by teachers, school leaders, and educators;
- preferred types of educational materials and resources;
- the role of schools and families in prevention and empowerment strategies.

In particular, the group discussions highlighted the need to address different forms of online violence, including the continuum between online and offline experiences, as well as issues related to social isolation, exclusion, and passive versus active online behaviours. Strong emphasis was placed on the importance of engaging parents and strengthening collaboration between schools and families as a key element of prevention and empowerment strategies.

In terms of knowledge and skills, participants stressed the need to develop coping skills, especially with regard to psychological and emotional aspects, alongside educators' competences in recognising and dealing with cyberbullying and online risks before, during and after critical incidents. The discussions also pointed to the need for increased digital awareness and practical guidance on the use of devices and social media, not only for students but also for teachers and parents, taking into account differences in age, experience, and confidence with technology.

Regarding educational materials and resources, school representatives expressed a preference for short, accessible, and practice-oriented tools, such as brief videos suitable for social media, visual materials, short tutorials, and lesson plans for teachers. Participants also highlighted the value of good practices, concrete examples, and adaptable strategies, rather than one-size-fits-all solutions, as well as the importance of creating safe spaces for dialogue, where concerns and experiences related to social media use can be openly discussed.

Overall, the needs analysis confirmed the relevance of a systemic and flexible approach, capable of responding to diverse school contexts, supporting educators' training needs, and fostering collaboration between schools, families, and local communities.

Conclusion and evaluation

The day, and the CCW as a whole, concluded with a collective discussion and evaluation, reinforcing the role of schools as active co-creators of project outcomes rather than passive recipients. The overall assessment of the workshop was highly positive, with 100% positive feedback from local participants and 99.2% positive feedback from project partners.

Qualitative feedback highlighted the relevance of the workshop in providing concrete ideas and good practices that participants could transfer to their school contexts, particularly with regard to renewing school rules and procedures, addressing cyberbullying, and strengthening collaboration with parents. Participants also valued the opportunity to explore different approaches adopted by schools, to exchange experiences, and to establish contacts for networking at both national and transnational level.

In addition, both local participants and partners emphasised the inspirational value of the transdisciplinary exchange, the presence of multiple perspectives and professional backgrounds, and the positive working climate, which was perceived as open, well-organised and conducive to discussion. Overall, the first CCW contributed to consolidating a shared methodological and

conceptual framework for the project, while also supporting preparation and alignment for subsequent workshops and activities.

2.3. 2nd ASAP Co-Creation Workshop (Porto, Portugal)

The second ASAP CCW was held in Porto, Portugal, from 5 to 7 September 2023, and hosted by the Universidade Lusófona do Porto. Building on the methodological and conceptual foundations established during the first CCW in Maribor, the Porto workshop further developed the ASAP co-creation approach, with a stronger emphasis on design-thinking processes and on the co-design of educational models, programmes, and tools.

As in the Maribor CCW, the workshop was articulated over three days and functioned as a point of convergence for ongoing activities across the different work packages, linking research, educational design and the preparation of future piloting activities, with a specific focus on collaborative and design-oriented processes.

Thematic focus and objectives

The Porto CCW focused on the overarching topic “Social media as democratic spaces to grow and to learn”. This thematic focus aimed to explore social media not only as environments associated with risks and challenges, but also as potential spaces for learning, participation, and citizenship-building, particularly for pre-adolescents.

The specific objectives of the workshop were to:

- critically reflect on the opportunities, risks, and limitations of using social media in educational and citizenship-oriented contexts;
- explore how social media platforms may support or hinder democratic engagement, inclusion, and participation among pre-teens;
- integrate perspectives from different disciplines and professional fields, including education, media studies, digital literacy, and citizenship education;
- actively involve local school representatives and experts in the co-design of educational approaches and tools;
- contribute concrete inputs to the development of the ASAP Educational Model and Programme.

As in the previous CCW, participants were encouraged to adopt a metacognitive and reflective stance, paying attention not only to the content of the discussions but also to the reasoning processes and assumptions underlying their analyses.

Participants

The workshop brought together 10 representatives of the project partner organisations, alongside 24 local school representatives and 5 Portuguese experts with experience in digital education, online safety, media literacy, and citizenship education, as well as co-design methodologies.

As in the previous CCW, group composition was intentionally heterogeneous, supporting cross-country comparison and mutual learning, while anchoring discussions in educational practice and design-oriented collaboration.

CCW activities

In line with the approach adopted in Maribor, the Porto workshop was organised around a sequence of T-Lab sessions, which combined knowledge-sharing, facilitated group work and plenary discussion, with a stronger emphasis on collaborative and design-oriented activities.

Under the title “Social media as democratic spaces”, the first day introduced the thematic focus of the workshop and centred on a collective reflection on social media as democratic spaces.

T-Lab Session 1.1 adopted a Knowledge Café methodology, in which participants rotated across small groups to discuss a set of guiding questions related to:

- risks, challenges, and opportunities of using social media for education and citizenship education;
- inclusivity and the prevention of hate speech, online abuse, and risky behaviours;
- the engagement of pre-teens in democratic processes through social media platforms.

This format allowed participants to progressively build on each other’s reflections, identify critical issues, and highlight aspects requiring further attention in research and educational design. More specifically, the group discussions brought to light a number of cross-cutting themes related to the three guiding topics.

With regard to risks, challenges, and opportunities of using social media for education and citizenship education, groups highlighted the accessibility and attractiveness of social media as key opportunities, particularly in terms of engagement, interaction, and ease of access to information. At the same time, risks were associated with misunderstandings about appropriate use, the emotional impact of online interactions, and the lack of critical and reflective skills among children. Participants also stressed that schools and teachers are often not sufficiently equipped or prepared to address these issues, pointing to the need for targeted teacher training and continuous professional development in rapidly evolving digital environments.

In relation to inclusivity and the prevention of hate speech, online abuse and risky behaviours, discussions focused on issues of judgement, exclusion, and inequality. Groups reflected on how social media dynamics (such as likes, dislikes and performance-oriented visibility) can reinforce comparison, stereotyping and lack of empathy, potentially leading to bullying and harassment. Particular attention was paid to algorithmic biases, access to digital resources, and the risk of reproducing social and cultural inequalities online. Participants also questioned whether genuinely inclusive and non-judgemental digital spaces are achievable, and emphasised the importance of educational approaches that promote critical interpretation, empathy, and awareness of how judgements are constructed both online and offline.

Finally, regarding the engagement of pre-teens in democratic processes through social media, participants explored the tension between protection and participation. Discussions highlighted the importance of supporting pre-teens in understanding democratic processes, rights, and responsibilities, while also developing social and communication skills such as listening to different points of view, expressing opinions, and engaging respectfully with others. Groups emphasised the need to create opportunities for young people to have a voice (through formats such as discussions, storytelling, or moderated online participation) while recognising the crucial role of schools and families in accompanying and mediating children’s engagement in digital democratic spaces.

T-Lab Session 1.2 focused on the analysis of specific social media platforms most commonly used by children and pre-teens (YouTube, TikTok and Instagram). Working in groups, participants examined how these platforms influence democratic participation and citizenship-building, considering dimensions such as user engagement, political and social discourses, algorithmic biases, and safety policies related to hate speech and aggressive content. Group findings were then compared and discussed in plenary, highlighting both opportunities and structural risks associated with platform design.

For Instagram, participants noted the strong influence of visual content and influencers on opinions and attitudes, alongside the presence of safety tools (e.g. Family Center) that are not always known or fully understood by users. Discussions also pointed to algorithmic mechanisms that tend to repeatedly expose users to similar content, potentially limiting plurality of perspectives and reinforcing dominant narratives.

In relation to TikTok, groups emphasised high levels of engagement driven by features such as short videos, reactions and gamification, while also highlighting risks linked to oversharing, aggressive or polarised discourses, and a powerful algorithm that creates the illusion of active choice while reinforcing passive consumption and limited points of view. Concerns were also raised regarding age restrictions, privacy settings, and moderation practices.

For YouTube, participants underlined its strong capacity to engage diverse audiences through varied content formats and lengths, as well as its role as a major space for political and social discourse. At the same time, algorithmic recommendations, the presence of advertising and the complexity of reporting harmful content were identified as critical issues, particularly in relation to exposure to inappropriate or misleading information.

Overall, the comparison across platforms highlighted the need to address algorithmic awareness, critical engagement with content, and the balance between participation, protection, and safety as central dimensions for educational interventions targeting pre-teens.

The day also included a session titled “Playing with the algorithm”, which built on experiences from the ASAP Collaborative Editorial Board pilot activities and allowed participants to critically reflect on the role of algorithms in shaping visibility, engagement and learning experiences on social media.

The second day, entitled “Experts talk”, combined expert inputs and co-creation activities with local school representatives, with a specific focus on the Portuguese context. Expert talks addressed the theme “The Portuguese experience: growing up in a digital world”, with contributions from Andreia Martins (Democracia do Bem Comum), Tito Morais and Cristiane Miranda (Agarrados à Net), and Cláudia Manata (Alerta Premika! Risco Online Detetado), with the participation of ASAP partner staff member Teresa Sofia Castro.

Drawing on the experience of organisations and initiatives active in the fields of digital safety, digital learning and online risk prevention, these contributions provided contextualised insights into challenges and good practices related to children’s and adolescents’ digital lives in Portugal, and served as a basis for discussion with project partners and school representatives.

After the presentations, T-Lab Session 2.1 centred on media education, digital literacy, and citizenship in educational contexts. Mixed groups of partners and local school representatives engaged in a design-oriented activity aimed at co-creating draft lesson plans or teaching activities that teachers could implement in their classrooms. The activity encouraged participants to reflect on themes, objectives, approaches, target groups, materials, implementation strategies, and evaluation methods, ensuring a strong connection between theoretical reflection and classroom practice.

In this context, the co-design activity led to the identification of a range of concrete and adaptable teaching ideas, addressing different age groups and educational settings. Examples of activities proposed by the groups included scenario-based discussions on topics such as parental control and digital supervision, aimed at fostering critical thinking, dialogue between children and parents, and a better understanding of responsibility in digital environments. Other proposals focused on cyberbullying awareness, through the collection, reinterpretation and performance of stories using interactive formats such as theatre sketches, videos, comics, or visual materials, with the involvement of the wider school community.

Several groups also explored media and information literacy activities centred on the credibility of information and journalistic principles, for instance through podcast creation, analysis of sources, collaborative questioning, and discussion of multiple perspectives. Additional ideas addressed everyday media consumption practices, encouraging pupils and families to reflect together on habits, screen time, and digital behaviours, and to co-create shared rules or agreements. Overall, the proposed activities emphasised participatory, dialogic, and reflective approaches, combining classroom work with family and community involvement, and highlighting the importance of non-judgemental and inclusive educational practices.

Figure 2 and 3. Group sessions with teachers during the 2nd ASAP Co-Creation Workshop in Porto, Portugal

The session concluded with a collective discussion and mind-mapping exercise (T-Lab Session 2.2), synthesising key insights, opportunities, and threats related to promoting media and information literacy and citizenship education in formal educational settings.

The third day focused on "Building the Educational Model & Programme", with particular attention to the contribution of design-thinking approaches.

Following introductory talks on the challenges, usefulness and expected contributions of the educational model (including Italian and Portuguese experiences), participants took part in T-Lab Session 3.1, a practical design-thinking activity facilitated by Andreia Pinto de Sousa (Universidade Lusófona do Porto). Building on the conclusions of the previous days, groups worked on refining and conceptualising educational activities and programme components, considering usability, user needs, and pedagogical coherence.

The outcomes of this session contributed to shaping a preliminary vision of the ASAP Approach and Handbook, including initial indications on features, tools, and engagement strategies for the different target groups in the design and implementation phases.

Conclusion and evaluation

The Porto CCW concluded with a collective discussion and evaluation of both the workshop activities and the overall co-creation process. The overall assessment was very positive, with a 97.5% positive evaluation from local participants and a 99% positive evaluation from project partners, confirming the relevance and effectiveness of the workshop format and contents.

Qualitative feedback from local participants highlighted the practical value of the co-creation activities, particularly the possibility of translating ideas and proposals into concrete classroom practices and school-level initiatives. Participants emphasised the usefulness of the workshop in providing new ideas, projects and methodologies to be implemented with students, families and the wider school community, as well as the importance of actively involving children, listening to their perspectives and giving them a voice in activities designed for their own digital lives. The group work and co-design methodology was positively assessed as stimulating and participatory, fostering exchange among teachers and educators, networking, and mutual learning, while also revealing a strong interest in having more time to further develop and refine the proposed activities.

Feedback from project partners similarly stressed the effectiveness of the Knowledge Café and design-thinking approaches, as well as the relevance of expert inputs, particularly those addressing algorithmic processes and online risks. Partners noted that the activities and solutions developed during the workshop were strongly focused on target groups and could be readily transformed into learning activities, with appropriate adaptation. The overall climate of the workshop was described as pleasant, motivating, and productive, with social moments further supporting collaboration and cohesion among participants.

Overall, the Porto CCW significantly contributed to advancing the ASAP co-creation process, supporting the development of shared pedagogical approaches and reinforcing alignment among partners in view of the subsequent design, piloting, and implementation phases of the project.

2.4. 3rd ASAP Co-Creation Workshop (České Budějovice, Czechia)

The third ASAP Co-Creation Workshop (CCW) was held in České Budějovice, Czechia, from 8 to 10 April 2024, and hosted by ProEduca. The workshop marked a key milestone in the project lifecycle, as it was explicitly focused on the co-designing and testing of the ASAP Educational Programme in preparation for the launch of pilot activities in all partner countries, building on the conceptual foundations established during the previous CCWs in Maribor and Porto and on the emerging findings from the ASAP Desk and Field Research. In addition, within the framework of the CCW, the project hosted its first official dissemination event, the ASAP Mid-Term Conference, which took place on the third day of the workshop.

As in the previous CCWs, the workshop was articulated over three days and functioned as a point of convergence for ongoing activities across the different work packages, with a particular emphasis on translating research evidence and pilot experiences into concrete, testable educational activities, and programme structures.

Thematic focus and objectives

The Czech CCW focused on the overarching topic “Co-designing and testing the Educational Programme”. The workshop aimed to move from reflection and conceptualisation to hands-on experimentation, supporting partners in jointly defining learning units and activities in preparation for local pilots.

The specific objectives of the workshop were to:

- integrate insights from the ASAP Field Research conducted across partner countries;
- analyse and capitalise on the Italian pilot experience (Collaborative Editorial Board and Pilot 0);
- co-design, test and refine learning units and activities for different target groups;
- align educational design choices with evaluation and impact assessment frameworks;
- strengthen coherence between research, educational modelling, and piloting activities.

Throughout the workshop, participants were encouraged to adopt a reflective and metacognitive stance, explicitly connecting practice, theory, and design choices.

Participants

The CCW brought together 14 representatives from all project partner organisations, alongside 5 local school representatives, 2 school teachers and 3 schoolchildren, as well as 5 local and international experts who took part in the Mid-Term Conference. Together, the contributions of project partners and invited experts contributed to bringing transdisciplinary perspectives grounded in research and practice in media literacy, digital citizenship, cyberaggression, online risks and pre-adolescents’ wellbeing.

As in the previous CCWs, working groups were intentionally composed to ensure heterogeneity in terms of disciplinary background, professional role, country and experience, supporting cross-country comparison, mutual learning and collaborative problem-solving, while keeping educational practice and school-based perspectives central.

CCW activities

As in the previous CCWs, the Czech workshop was structured around a sequence of T-Lab sessions, combining expert inputs, group work, plenary discussion, and practical testing activities, with a strong focus on Educational Programme development and validation.

The first day focused on connecting practice from the Italian pilot experience and findings from the ongoing field research as foundations for educational design.

T-Lab Session 1 centred on the Italian Pilot Experience, with a presentation of the ASAP Collaborative Editorial Board (CEB) and Pilot 0. The session illustrated how learning modules were progressively developed, revised, and systematised into a first set of three learning units, highlighting the participatory processes through which students, teachers and experts contributed to shaping content and activities. This experience provided a concrete reference point for reflecting on how to complete the Educational Programme and Handbook, and on which pedagogical and methodological principles could be abstracted from practice and generalised within the ASAP Approach.

Building on this, partners explored the ASAP Educational Programme Framework starting from the first learning units identified, focusing on how these units bring together knowledge, skills, and abilities across transversal themes such as emotions, questions, authenticity, trust, and algorithmic awareness. The discussion contributed to a shared clarification of the structure and internal logic of the Educational Programme, contributing to the definition of a common structure for its further development.

T-Lab Session 2 was dedicated to the presentation and discussion of initial findings from the ASAP Field Research, with inputs from Slovenia, Italy, and the Czech Republic. Drawing on surveys, focus groups and interviews with pre-adolescents, parents, teachers and school leaders, partners highlighted a set of shared patterns across the three contexts. These included pre-adolescents' high familiarity with digital and social media environments, alongside limited opportunities for structured critical reflection on their online experiences, particularly in relation to emotions, peer dynamics, and credibility of information. The discussion also pointed to a misalignment between children's everyday digital practices and adults' understanding of them, with parents and educators often expressing uncertainty about how to support and mediate pre-adolescents' online lives in constructive ways. Overall, the findings emphasised the central role of communication and trust between children and adults, and the relevance of educational approaches grounded in dialogue and experience rather than control alone.

Building on these findings, the session concluded with group work and plenary discussion aimed at reflecting on how the priorities and needs identified through the research could be addressed within the Educational Programme. In particular, participants discussed how issues such as online risks and cyberaggression, emotional awareness, communication and trust, and credibility of information could be translated into learning units and activity formats. The discussion emphasised the importance of linking online experiences with offline relationships and emotions, strengthening questioning, critical thinking and dialogue, and supporting adult mediation strategies through flexible, experience-based activities adaptable to different school contexts.

The second day of the Czech CCW was dedicated to testing and refining the ASAP Educational Programme, with a specific focus on pilot preparation and evaluation. Activities were designed to move from conceptual discussion to hands-on experimentation, supporting partners in critically

assessing learning activities and programme components ahead of the launch of local pilots in all partner countries.

T-Lab Session 3 focused on Educational Programme Testing and Pilot preparation, building on activities developed during the Italian Pilot and within the emerging Educational Programme framework. In particular, participants tested selected activities from the Learning Unit Emotions, including activities such as “On Question... Image”, “Bingo” and “Emoji”, aimed at recognising, naming, and discussing primary and social emotions in relation to online and offline experiences. The testing process allowed participants to assess the clarity, feasibility, adaptability, and relevance of the activities for different target groups, including pre-adolescents, teachers, and parents. Group work and plenary discussion supported the collection of structured feedback on strengths, potential challenges and contextual adaptations needed for implementation in different national and school settings.

Figure 4 and 5. ASAP team testing the Emotions Learning Unit the 3rd Co-Creation Workshop in České Budějovice, Czechia

A dedicated session was then devoted to the Impact Evaluation Framework, addressing how pilot activities should be accompanied by coherent and meaningful evaluation processes. Participants discussed key questions related to what impact the Educational Programme aims to generate, how impact could be assessed over time, and which tools could be used with different target groups. The discussion addressed evaluation at both individual and group levels, considering multiple time points (initial assessment, short-term and medium-term follow-up) and reinforcing the link between educational objectives and impact evaluation criteria.

Following the discussion on pilot preparation and evaluation, participants engaged in a co-design session focused on consolidating the overall structure of the ASAP Educational Programme. Starting from a shared map of potential topics emerging from field research, pilot experiences and previous CCWs, the discussion aimed to identify learning units still to be developed and to clarify how existing and new topics could be organised into a coherent and comprehensive programme structure. Participants reflected on how transversal dimensions, such as emotions, questioning, authenticity, trust, media functioning, online risks, and communication, could be articulated into distinct but interconnected learning units, applicable across different target groups (pre-adolescents, teachers, and parents). This session contributed to defining the core structure of the Educational Programme, supporting its completion according to a shared framework and ensuring coherence between learning units, activities and underlying pedagogical principles.

The third day also hosted the ASAP Mid-Term Conference, which represented the project's first official dissemination event and was organised as part of the CCW to open the project's work to a wider audience of local and international stakeholders. The conference was articulated into three main sessions and was live-streamed via ProEduca's YouTube channel, reaching an average of approximately 40 online participants from different countries, in addition to those attending in person.

Beyond live participation, the conference showed a strong asynchronous reach, indicating significant interest beyond those attending in person or following the live stream. Already on the day following the event, each session had recorded more than 100 views, amounting to over 300 views overall, suggesting that many participants preferred to access the contents asynchronously. At the time of writing, the first session dedicated to the ASAP project has exceeded 500 views, while the second and third sessions have each surpassed 200 views, reaching a total of over 900 cumulative views. These figures further confirm the relevance of the topics addressed and the effectiveness of online dissemination in extending the project's outreach.

The [first session](#) was dedicated to the ASAP project and its progress, with a focus on research and early implementation experiences. It included a presentation of the project framework and objectives, the first results of the ASAP Field Research, and a specific focus on the Czech Field Research findings. The session also featured the presentation of the Italian pilot experience, with particular attention to the role and functioning of the ASAP Collaborative Editorial Board.

The [second session](#) featured expert contributions addressing key dimensions of young people's digital lives. David Smahel (Masaryk University) presented on *The risks of children's digital media use and the impact of digital media use on wellbeing*, offering research-based insights into online risks and their psychosocial implications. Dana Robota (County Center for Educational Resources and Assistance, Iași) contributed a perspective on *Digital citizenship approaches for Romanian students*, focusing on educational strategies to foster participation and responsibility online. Christine Trültzsch-Wijnen (Charles University) discussed *Media literacy and media socialization of young people*, highlighting the role of media education in shaping young people's socialisation processes.

The [third session](#) further explored research- and practice-based perspectives through additional expert inputs. Marie Jaroň Bedrošová (Masaryk University) presented on *Children's and adolescents' experiences with cyberaggression*, addressing forms, dynamics and impacts of online aggression.

Markéta Supá (Charles University) focused on *Underage activism and social networks*, discussing how social media can act as spaces for civic engagement as well as sources of tension and risk.

Overall, the conference contributions highlighted clear areas of convergence between research evidence and the ASAP project's conceptual and educational trajectory, reinforcing the relevance of the proposed Educational Programme and the need for structured, research-informed educational interventions in this field.

In the afternoon, the CCW continued with practical testing activities involving local participants, focusing on selected activities from the Learning Unit Emotions in preparation for the launch of pilot activities in the partner countries. This testing phase allowed partners to observe participant engagement, gather qualitative feedback, and further assess the feasibility, clarity, and adaptability of the activities in educational settings. The session contributed to fine-tuning the activities ahead of the pilot phase, while confirming the relevance of hands-on, experience-based approaches for working with pre-adolescents and educational communities.

Conclusion and evaluation

The CCW concluded with a collective wrap-up and evaluation, confirming the role of the Czech workshop as a key transition point between programme design and large-scale piloting, and strengthening alignment among partners ahead of the implementation phase.

The overall assessment of the workshop was very positive. The activities involving local participants received a 100% positive evaluation, while project partners expressed a 97.8% positive assessment, confirming the relevance of the workshop format and its focus on testing, co-design, and programme consolidation. In addition, the ASAP Mid-Term Conference held within the CCW was evaluated very positively by registered conference participants, both live and asynchronous viewers, with an overall 98% satisfaction rate, highlighting the relevance of the topics addressed and the quality of the partner and expert contributions.

Qualitative feedback from the Mid-Term Conference further emphasised the usefulness and timeliness of the issues discussed, particularly in relation to digital education, online risks, cyberaggression, media literacy and children's wellbeing. Participants highlighted the value of gaining research-based insights, exchanging perspectives across countries, and acquiring ideas applicable to their professional and educational contexts. This feedback, together with the high level of online participation and asynchronous engagement, confirmed the conference's effectiveness as a dissemination and dialogue initiative.

Overall, the Czech CCW played a crucial role in consolidating the ASAP Educational Programme, supporting its completion according to a shared structure and principles, and preparing partners for the pilot implementation phase. At the same time, the integration of the Mid-Term Conference strengthened the project's external visibility and reinforced the alignment between research evidence and the project's educational approach.

2.5. 4th ASAP Co-Creation Workshop (Zagreb, Croatia)

The fourth ASAP Co-Creation Workshop (CCW) was held in Zagreb, Croatia, from 9 to 11 September 2024, and hosted by DKMK. The workshop represented a crucial step in the ASAP project, as it was primarily dedicated to the testing, validation, and consolidation of the ASAP Educational Programme, supporting the continuation and expansion of pilot activities across partner countries.

Building on the conceptual development carried out during the previous CCWs in Maribor, Porto and České Budějovice, the Zagreb CCW marked the transition from programme design to large-scale piloting, focusing on the practical implementation, usability, and adaptability of multiple Learning Units with different target groups. As in previous workshops, the CCW functioned as a hinge point between work packages, with a strong connection between WP3 (Educational Model and Programme), WP4 (Piloting) and WP5 (Educator Training).

Thematic focus and objectives

The Zagreb CCW focused on the overarching topic “Co-designing and co-testing the Educational Programme”, with particular emphasis on supporting the expansion of pilot activities and on the feedback-driven refinement of the Learning Units. The workshop aimed to test a selection of Educational Programme activities in authentic educational settings, involving both adults and pre-adolescents.

The specific objectives of the workshop were to:

- test selected Learning Units with teachers and students in real educational contexts;
- collect structured feedback on the clarity, feasibility, and relevance of activities;
- refine learning activities and pedagogical approaches based on testing outcomes;
- strengthen alignment between Educational Programme content, pilot implementation, and evaluation strategies.

Throughout the workshop, as in the previous CCWs, participants were invited to critically reflect on testing experiences, considering how observed reactions, feedback and constraints could inform educational objectives, pedagogical choices, and implementation decisions.

Participants

The CCW brought together 16 representatives of the project partner organisations, alongside 16 local teachers, 42 students aged 11–13, as well as 4 local experts. The involvement of different target groups allowed partners to test Learning Units in diverse formats and contexts, and to compare perspectives from educators, learners, and observers.

As in previous CCWs, working groups were intentionally composed to ensure heterogeneity in disciplinary background, professional roles and experience, supporting collaborative analysis, peer learning, and the integration of research-based and practice-oriented perspectives.

CCW activities

The first day of the Zagreb CCW was dedicated to an internal testing of selected Learning Units of the ASAP Educational Programme, carried out among project partners. Testing was organised through facilitated sessions led by the partner organisations responsible for each Learning Unit, with the other

partners participating in the activities. This format established a shared testing setting, allowing partners to observe facilitation approaches and to reflect collectively on the implementation logic of the Educational Programme.

The first session focused on the testing of selected activities from the Learning Units Authenticity and Authority, Role Models, Communication, and Onlife. Working in pairs or small groups, project partners engaged in the activities from a dual perspective, alternating between the role of participants and that of educators. This approach supported reflection on the structure and flow of the activities, as well as on facilitation strategies, timing and required materials.

Throughout the session, discussion concentrated on how the tested activities addressed transversal educational dimensions, including critical thinking, emotional awareness, communication skills, and media literacy, and on how they encouraged reflection on the interplay between online and offline experiences. Particular attention was given to the clarity of instructions, the balance between guidance and openness, and the extent to which activities promoted dialogue and active participation rather than prescriptive or rule-based learning.

The session concluded with a plenary synthesis, during which participants shared observations on strengths, challenges, and potential areas for improvement. This collective reflection supported the fine-tuning of the Learning Units and informed the selection and preparation of the activities considered most relevant for testing with local target groups during the following days of the workshop.

The second day of the Zagreb CCW combined expert contributions and hands-on work with local teachers, with the dual aim of contextualising the Educational Programme within the Croatian setting and further testing and refining selected Learning Units from an educational practice perspective.

The day opened with a series of expert inputs, addressed both to project partners and local teachers. Contributions focused on the Croatian context as well as on broader themes related to digital and media literacy, online risks, and educational responses. Expert inputs were provided by Viktorija Car (University of Split), Juraj Petrović (University of Zagreb) and Igor Kanižaj (Catholic University of Croatia, DKMK) and, offering complementary perspectives grounded in research, policy, and educational practice. These contributions helped frame the subsequent activities with teachers and reinforced the relevance of the Educational Programme in relation to current challenges faced by schools.

Following the expert inputs, the workshop moved to collaborative activities with local teachers, structured around two complementary formats.

First, teachers took part in the testing of selected activities from the Learning Unit The Power of Questions. Through facilitated sessions, participants experienced the activities directly and reflected on how questioning, critical thinking and dialogue could be fostered in classroom contexts. Discussion focused on clarity of instructions, appropriateness for the target age group, and the potential of the activities to support reflective and participatory learning processes.

Second, teachers engaged in small-group work focused on the activity sheets of different Learning Units. This activity aimed to verify the clarity, completeness, and usability of the activity descriptions, taking into account that these materials are intended to be used autonomously by educators during piloting and implementation. Teachers reviewed both the structure of the activity sheets and the

proposed content, providing feedback on language, level of detail, sequencing of steps and support for facilitation, as well as on educational relevance.

Figure 6. Group session with teachers during the 4th ASAP Co-Creation Workshop in Zagreb, Croatia

The day concluded with a shared reflection and evaluation moment, during which teachers and partners discussed key observations, strengths and areas for improvement emerging from the testing activities. This collective feedback contributed to refining both the activities and the supporting materials, and provided concrete indications for their further use within the Educational Programme and the ongoing piloting phase.

The third day of the Zagreb CCW was dedicated to testing selected Learning Units with students from a local school in Zagreb, to observe how the Educational Programme functioned in an authentic classroom setting and gather direct feedback from pre-adolescents. Two classes, involving a total of 42 students aged 11–13, took part in the activities. For the testing, students were divided into three working groups of 10, 12 and 20 participants, allowing for differentiated testing and observation.

During the sessions, students engaged in activities drawn from several Learning Units, including Authenticity and Authority, Communication, Onlife, Role Models, and The Power of Questions. The activities were facilitated by project partners and adapted to the classroom context, intending to encourage active participation, dialogue, and reflection on students' everyday online and offline experiences.

Despite the presence of a language barrier, as most activities were conducted in English by non-Croatian partners, except for Role Models, which was implemented in Croatian, students showed high levels of engagement and participation. Observations highlighted students' willingness to take part in discussions, games, and collaborative tasks, as well as their ability to relate the proposed themes to

their own experiences. The testing confirmed that the activities were stimulating and accessible, while also providing valuable insights into mediation and facilitation strategies.

At the end of the activities, students were invited to complete a short evaluation questionnaire, which collected both quantitative and qualitative feedback. Overall, the activities were positively received, with 81.3% of participants expressing a positive evaluation of the experience. In addition, 85.9% of respondents indicated that they would recommend the activities to peers of their age.

Qualitative feedback further illustrated how students perceived the activities as engaging, interactive and different from regular classroom lessons. Recurring themes in the responses included appreciation for game-based and interactive formats, opportunities for discussion and self-expression, working with peers, and reflecting on social media, apps, and online behaviours. Several students highlighted the value of being able to talk freely, share opinions and connect the activities to their own digital experiences. Suggestions for improvement mainly concerned practical aspects, such as having more time for activities, simplifying some instructions, or conducting the sessions in the local language, rather than the substance of the activities themselves.

Overall, the testing with students provided valuable confirmation of the relevance and attractiveness of the Educational Programme for pre-adolescents, while also generating concrete indications for further refinement, particularly in relation to language adaptation, pacing and facilitation. These insights contributed to informing the continued development and implementation of the ASAP Educational Programme within the ongoing piloting phase.

Following the testing activities with students, partners gathered for a shared reflection session focused specifically on the classroom-based implementation. The discussion centred on students' levels of engagement, comprehension, and participation, as well as on facilitation aspects such as group dynamics and timing. This exchange allowed partners to consolidate observations from the different groups and to identify common strengths and points for improvement to be addressed in the further refinement of their Learning Units and activities.

Conclusion and evaluation

The Zagreb CCW concluded with a collective wrap-up and evaluation, confirming its role as a key consolidation moment within the ASAP co-creation process. By combining internal testing among partners with classroom-based experimentation involving teachers and students, the workshop provided a rich and articulated set of inputs to support the continued piloting and refinement of the Educational Programme.

Overall, partners positively assessed the workshop format and outcomes, with a 99.2% positive rating, particularly the opportunity to observe how different Learning Units functioned in authentic educational settings and with diverse target groups, which was described as a particularly valuable and exemplary aspect of the CCW organisation. The direct testing with students was considered especially valuable in highlighting levels of engagement, accessibility, and relevance of the activities, as well as in revealing practical aspects related to facilitation, group dynamics, and timing. Partners also highlighted the added value of combining hands-on testing with expert inputs, which supported both professional reflection and personal understanding of key issues such as the role of algorithms in young people's digital lives.

Added to the positive evaluation of the students' activities, the feedback from teachers involved on the second day was also extremely positive, with a 100% positive evaluation rate. Qualitative feedback highlighted the relevance and usability of the proposed activities, particularly the availability of concrete examples, experiential learning approaches and adaptable tools that teachers felt could be readily transferred to their classroom practice. Participants valued the opportunity to exchange experiences with colleagues, to reflect on social media challenges and generational dynamics, and to acquire new perspectives and ideas in the field of media education. The workshops were described as motivating, well-structured and professionally enriching, with several teachers expressing appreciation for being actively listened to and involved, as well as a strong interest in participating in similar initiatives and future training opportunities.

Overall, the Zagreb CCW further strengthened alignment among partners around shared pedagogical principles and implementation priorities. The insights generated through testing and evaluation contributed to consolidating the Educational Programme and to informing its continued use and refinement within the ongoing piloting phase across partner countries.

2.6. 5th ASAP Co-Creation Workshop (Milan, Italy)

The fifth ASAP Co-Creation Workshop (CCW) was held in Milan, Italy, from 10 to 12 February 2025, and was hosted across three venues: ICS Bresso (Day 1), Fondazione Politecnico di Milano (Day 2), and Pepita (Day 3).

The Milan CCW represented a strategic consolidation moment in the second half of the project, bringing together lessons learned from the ASAP Field Research (WP2), continued work on the Collaborative Editorial Board (CEB) experience (WP6), and focused co-creation sessions linked to impact assessment (WP4), educator training (WP5) and policy recommendations (WP7), and supporting a coherent alignment between educational design, implementation and exploitation activities.

Thematic focus and objectives

In line with the CCW methodology, the Milan workshop functioned as a hinge point among ongoing work packages and as a space for aligning research evidence, educational practice, and exploitation-oriented outputs.

The workshop aimed to:

- consolidate cross-country lessons learned from the ASAP Field Research and reflect on how these insights informed ongoing activities and results;
- reconnect the co-creation process with school-based practice through direct interaction with the CEB students at ICS Bresso;
- advance shared work on the ASAP Educator Training Programme (WP5), strengthening coherence between programme content, facilitation strategies, and piloting needs;
- progress from project evidence to exploitation and policy-oriented outputs by structuring lessons learned into actionable policy recommendations (WP7);
- further refine the project's approach to assessing the impact of the ASAP Educational Programme (WP4), linking educational objectives, tools, and evaluation logic.

Participants

The workshop brought together 19 project partner representatives and, in selected sessions, 23 local participants, including 14 students, as well as 3 invited experts, ensuring a continued connection between research-based reflection, educational design and real-world school experiences.

CCW activities

The first day of the Milan CCW took place at ICS Bresso and was primarily dedicated to consolidating lessons learned from the ASAP Field Research and reconnecting these insights with ongoing co-creation processes involving students through the Collaborative Editorial Board (CEB).

The morning sessions focused on a structured reflection on the ASAP Field Research, building on consolidated cross-country data collected through surveys, focus groups and interviews. Partners shared and discussed key findings from the participating countries with teachers and the school leader from ICS Bresso, highlighting recurring patterns related to pre-adolescents' digital practices, online risks, emotional dimensions of media use, communication and trust between children and adults, and mediation strategies adopted by families and schools. Particular attention was paid to similarities and

differences across national contexts, as well as to how research findings resonated with concrete classroom experiences and had already informed the design of Learning Units and educational activities developed within the project. Alongside the presentation of research evidence, teachers actively contributed observations from their daily school practice, sharing challenges encountered in working with pre-adolescents and in engaging families around issues related to digital and social media use.

These discussions supported a shared understanding of how field research findings and school-based experiences could be further integrated into the ASAP Educational Programme, reinforcing the relevance of dialogic, experience-based and non-prescriptive approaches, and clarifying priority areas to be addressed in subsequent training, piloting and policy-oriented activities.

In the afternoon, the workshop shifted its focus to WP6 activities with the Collaborative Editorial Board. A dedicated session was held with CEB students from ICS Bresso, who were at the final stage of their CEB pathway, during which they had simulated the work of an editorial team to explore how information is produced, selected, and circulated. In this concluding phase of their “journalistic” experience, students took part in an interactive and facilitated exchange in which they interviewed project partners on topics related to social media, digital practices, and the broader themes of the ASAP project.

Alongside questions linked to the project’s educational focus, students also asked more personal and professional questions, reflecting their curiosity about partners’ backgrounds, roles, and experiences. The activity had a primarily relational and participatory function, offering students the opportunity to situate their CEB work within a wider European project context and to interact directly with partners from different countries.

For project partners, the session provided an informal but meaningful occasion to engage with students’ perspectives, language, and interests, and to observe how young people articulate questions and reflections at the end of a structured media education pathway. While not designed as a formal testing activity, the exchange nonetheless reinforced the value of involving pre-adolescents as active participants in the project, contributing to a shared sense of ownership and to the ongoing reflection on how the ASAP Educational Programme connects with students’ lived experiences.

Following the session with the CEB students, project partners reconvened for an internal debriefing focused on the earlier discussion of the ASAP Field Research with teachers. This moment of reflection allowed partners to revisit key points emerging from the exchange with school staff, to consider how teachers’ observations and challenges complemented the research evidence. In particular, the discussion helped to consolidate priorities related to adult mediation, communication with families and the translation of research findings into training, piloting, and policy-oriented activities.

The second day of the Milan CCW took place at Fondazione Politecnico di Milano and was primarily dedicated to advancing co-creation work linked to educator training (WP5) and policy-oriented reflection (WP7), while keeping the ASAP Educational Programme (WP3) at the centre of the discussion.

The morning sessions focused on the development of the ASAP Educator Training Programme, in view of its forthcoming piloting phase. Building on insights from previous CCWs, piloting experiences and field research findings, partners worked collaboratively to reflect on the structure, objectives, and

target groups of the training programme. Discussions addressed key questions related to the role of educators as mediators of children's digital and social media experiences, the balance between theoretical inputs and experiential learning, and the need for flexible training formats adaptable to different national and institutional contexts. Particular attention was paid to ensuring coherence between the Educational Programme and the training activities, so that educators would be supported not only in understanding the ASAP approach but also in confidently implementing Learning Units in practice.

In continuity with this reflection, partners also focused on clarifying the profile, competencies and practical needs of educators involved in delivering the ASAP Educational Programme. Drawing on the draft ASAP Educator Profile and on the interconnections between WP3 and WP5, the discussion addressed the key competences required to facilitate the Learning Units effectively, including digital and media literacy, socio-emotional facilitation, metacognitive guidance, activity adaptation, and inclusive classroom management skills. Particular attention was paid to positioning educators primarily as facilitators and mediators rather than content transmitters, and to aligning the training pathway with existing European reference frameworks such as DigCompEdu. This session contributed to refining the structure and focus of the Educator Training Programme ahead of its piloting phase, ensuring coherence between educational content, facilitation skills, and evaluation requirements.

In the afternoon, the workshop shifted towards exploitation and policy-oriented reflection (WP7). Starting from consolidated evidence emerging from the ASAP Field Research, CCWs and pilot experiences, partners engaged in structured group work aimed at identifying key messages, priorities, and recommendations relevant for schools, families, policymakers, and other stakeholders. The discussion focused on how to translate project findings into actionable recommendations, addressing issues such as digital education in schools, prevention of online risks and cyberaggression, educator training needs, and the role of schools and families in supporting children's digital wellbeing.

More concretely, the policy-oriented group work highlighted a set of recurring priorities across target groups. These included the need to recognise children's and pre-adolescents' digital lives as a shared educational responsibility between schools, families, and institutions, moving beyond purely technical or tool-based approaches. Participants emphasised the importance of strengthening listening skills, dialogue, and trust-building as core educational and preventive strategies, alongside early, continuous, and age-appropriate digital education embedded across the school curriculum rather than confined to isolated activities.

Further priorities concerned the active involvement of parents through accessible guidance and shared responsibility frameworks, support for teachers through dedicated training and practical tools, and the recognition of schools as key social infrastructures requiring time, resources, and institutional backing to address digital and online challenges effectively. For policymakers, discussions stressed the need to create enabling conditions—through coherent policies, cross-sector collaboration, and sustained investment—that support preventive, participatory and experience-based approaches to digital education and wellbeing.

Throughout the day, individual, group, and plenary work allowed partners to connect the different strands of work (educational design, training, and policy) highlighting interdependencies and reinforcing the project's overall implementation and exploitation strategy.

The third day of the Milan CCW took place at Pepita and was dedicated to advancing work on impact assessment (WP4), while consolidating links between the ASAP Educational Programme, educator training, and policy-oriented outputs.

The morning session opened with a visit to the newly established ReTe Centre, promoted by Fondazione Carolina in collaboration with Pepita. The centre represents an innovative support hub dedicated to the prevention of online risks and cyberviolence, offering integrated educational, psychological, and legal support to children, adolescents, families, and schools. The visit provided partners with a concrete example of a multi-professional and community-based approach to digital wellbeing, highlighting how prevention, support and educational action can be structurally embedded within local services and school ecosystems.

After the visit to the ReTe Centre, the morning sessions focused on advancing the ASAP impact assessment framework (WP4). Building on discussions held during previous CCWs and on insights emerging from early piloting activities, partners worked collaboratively to refine a shared approach to evaluating the impact of the Educational Programme across different target groups and contexts. The discussion addressed key questions related to the types of change the programme aims to generate, the definition of meaningful indicators, and the balance between qualitative and quantitative evaluation tools, with particular attention to feasibility and sustainability in real school settings.

More concretely, partners engaged in a structured “designing on change” activity, aimed at clarifying the intended educational and relational changes associated with the Learning Units. Through guided reflection and hands-on work, including the use of LEGO as a visual and participatory tool, participants explored what kinds of changes they expect to observe in students’ knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behaviours, and how these changes could manifest in everyday situations. This work supported the identification of concrete change dimensions and informed the development of the ASAP impact evaluation tools, including situational activities and observational grids designed to capture both individual learning outcomes and group dynamics over time.

Figure 7. ASAP team after the Change Design LEGO activity session at the 5th Co-Creation Workshop in Milan, Italy

In the afternoon, the workshop included a session with invited experts, who contributed complementary perspectives on digital wellbeing, education and regulation in children's and adolescents' online lives. Giulia Cimpanelli, journalist at *la Repubblica* and editor of the *Becoming Digital Parents* column, reflected on the challenges of parenting and family mediation in a highly mediatised environment, highlighting tensions, responsibilities and opportunities linked to growing up online. Riccardo Lanzo, lawyer specialising in image rights and intellectual property, addressed legal aspects related to social media use, content creation and platform dynamics, with particular attention to rights, responsibilities, and protection in digital contexts. Paolo Ferri, Professor of Education and Special Pedagogy at the University of Milan-Bicocca, offered a pedagogical perspective on digital learning environments, focusing on the role of media and technologies in supporting reflective, participatory, and meaningful educational practices.

The session was followed by a collective discussion that connected these expert inputs with the project's research findings and educational experiences, contributing to the identification and refinement of key recommendations relevant for schools, families, and policymakers.

Overall, the third day reinforced the integration between impact assessment, educational practice, and policy reflection, consolidating shared assumptions and tools ahead of the final phases of the project.

Conclusion and evaluation

The Milan CCW concluded with a collective wrap-up and evaluation, in continuity with the CCW methodology adopted across the project. The workshop confirmed its role as a key consolidation moment in the second half of the ASAP project, bringing together research evidence, school-based practice, educator training design, impact assessment and policy reflection, and reinforcing a shared perspective on sustainability through training, capacity building and policy-oriented outputs.

Partners positively assessed the workshop format and outcomes, with a 96.9% positive evaluation rate, particularly valuing the opportunity to work in a highly integrated manner across work packages and to connect strategic reflection with concrete tools and practices. The combination of interaction with local schools and students, focused co-creation sessions among partners, and dialogue with external experts was considered especially valuable in strengthening the coherence, maturity, and readiness of the project's outputs.

Feedback from local participants was also largely positive, with a 91.7% positive evaluation rate. Qualitative comments, though limited in number, highlighted the relevance of the workshop in reinforcing awareness of the importance of listening, dialogue and mediation within families.

From a methodological perspective, the Milan CCW further confirmed the relevance of the co-creation approach adopted throughout the project, highlighting the value of iterative reflection and alignment between educational design, implementation, and evaluation. The insights generated during the workshop directly informed the consolidation of the impact assessment framework, the refinement of the Educator Training Programme, and the structuring of policy-oriented recommendations, supporting the transition towards the final implementation, exploitation, and sustainability phases of the ASAP project.

3. Conclusions

The ASAP Co-Creation Workshops have played a central role in shaping the Educational Model and Programme by providing a structured, iterative, and practice-oriented space for collaboration across countries, disciplines and target groups. Rather than functioning as standalone events, the CCWs supported a cumulative learning process in which research evidence, educational design, testing, evaluation and reflection were progressively aligned and refined over time.

Across the five workshops, the co-creation methodology proved effective in maintaining a continuous dialogue between conceptual reflection and concrete educational practice. The gradual shift from needs analysis and conceptual exploration towards hands-on testing, consolidation and impact-oriented work allowed the Educational Programme to be developed in close connection with real school contexts, educators' professional experiences and the lived realities of pre-adolescents. This process helped ensure that the Programme remained adaptable, context-sensitive and grounded in everyday educational challenges.

A key added value of the CCWs was their function as spaces of listening and mutual learning with local target groups and invited experts. The systematic involvement of teachers, school leaders, students, families and professionals from different fields contributed to validating assumptions, revealing blind spots and enriching the programme with perspectives that could not have emerged from partner work alone. At the same time, the transnational dimension of the workshops supported cross-country comparison and the identification of shared patterns alongside contextual differences.

From a methodological standpoint, the CCWs confirmed the relevance of experience-based, dialogic and non-prescriptive approaches when addressing digital and social media issues with pre-adolescents. The workshops consistently highlighted the importance of mediation, questioning, emotional awareness, and trust-building as transversal educational dimensions, reinforcing the project's systemic perspective on digital education and wellbeing.

Overall, the Co-Creation Workshops contributed to consolidating the ASAP Educational Programme, strengthening its internal coherence and its alignment with research findings, training needs, evaluation frameworks, and policy-oriented considerations. In doing so, they supported the project's transition towards its final implementation, exploitation, and sustainability phases, providing a shared foundation for the continued use, adaptation, and transfer of ASAP results beyond the project duration.

This report is part of the Erasmus+ project ASAP – *A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education*.

It documents the ASAP Co-Creation Workshops, a core methodological component of the project designed to support the collaborative development of the ASAP Educational Model and Programme. Implemented between March 2023 and February 2025 in the five partner countries (Slovenia, Portugal, Czechia, Croatia and Italy), the workshops brought together project partners, experts, teachers and educators and, in selected phases, pre-adolescents, within structured transnational and transdisciplinary learning spaces. Through an iterative co-creation process, the workshops supported the integration of research evidence, educational practice and piloting experiences, contributing to the progressive refinement, testing and consolidation of the project's educational approach.

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